

Requirements on Information Models for Smart Road Services

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Abstract—Smart road services and automated driving are relatively young and highly dynamic fields of development. Standardization and harmonization efforts are driven by different stakeholders in the industry and many of the existing works address the development and safety of automated driving functions. However, the vast complexity and the international dimension of the endeavour of automated driving in general, and the complexity of individual tasks to be automated make it necessary that promising efforts converge towards a widely accepted, applicable and relatively stable framework for joint development. Towards this vision, this work argues that for smart road services, communication between participants at the information level (as opposed to data or signal levels of the DIKW pyramid) is most advantageous. An information model that describes all conceivably relevant information for smart road services must be developed. To this end, a list of requirements that such an information model should meet is proposed and each requirement is argued for. Lastly, it is shown that and in what way the road infrastructure can support automated driving, assuming a suitable information model exists.

Index Terms—Information Model, Ontology, Smart Road, Automated Driving, ODD, ISAD

I. INTRODUCTION

IN this work a formulation of requirements on information models for smart road services is proposed. Smart road services encompass automated and autonomous driving functions that generally rely on the exchange of information between agents and infrastructure. Current scientific and application-oriented discourse does not distinguish strictly between information and data, which leads to a plethora of conflicting requirements formulated by sensor manufacturers, infrastructure operators and developers of automated and autonomous driving functions. An argument as to why *information* is the appropriate level of abstraction is made by utilizing a working example. Once the target level of abstraction is established, a coherent set of requirements can be derived to support real world implementation.

Let us start with an example. Consider a road section with a speed limit. Currently there is an ongoing discussion whether or not the road signs indicating the existence of these limits on the road side need to be machine readable in some way. This could be achieved for instance by high reflective signs or by extending the sign by a QR-code visible in the infrared range, just to name two suggestions. However, a study receiving considerable attention showed that road signs which rely on camera detection can be deceived quite easily [1], indicating an entirely new attack vector if used intentionally, or a proper safety risk for soiled or damaged signs. This indicates that the delivery of relevant information in machine-readable format to the vehicle is a safety critical task.

Is there a possible solution to the problem described above? In this paper we would like to lift this (and similar) discussion(s) to a higher level and show that this might not even be the proper question to ask. Let us take a step back and look once again at our section of road with a speed limit. What does a driver actually need to know in order to pass this section in compliance with regulations? When reading "speed limit" we likely think about the corresponding physical sign, as it typically looks like in our country of residence. This is not surprising, since this is the commonly used approach to inform the drivers about the regulations that are valid in the upcoming road section, which end at the respective cancellation sign. But traffic signs are not the exclusive means how a driver or a vehicle (with an automation level that requires such capabilities) can obtain information about the speed limit. In fact, we are also used to a different kind of information flow. A navigation system in the car also knows about a considerable number of speed limits without needing to know about the physical existence of the road signs. It typically holds an additional map layer in which position, range of validity and the corresponding speed limit or restriction are encoded. When entering the area of validity, the navigation system might present this information to the driver. Typically this is achieved by showing an image of the actual speed limit sign on a display, since this is the way human drivers are used to obtain this information. But there are other ways, for example, one could also imagine a voice output indicating the upcoming speed limit.

Having thought through this specific example, we see that the relevant information needed by a driver, in order to be able to drive accordingly, is the speed limits scope and value. This holds for both human or automated drivers. The information has to exist and has to be delivered in some way to the driver. The way the information is transmitted to the driver is not really relevant as long as it is reliable. Note that in this definition we do not depend on the existence of road signs (machine readable or not).

II. A COMMUNICATION-ORIENTED PERSPECTIVE ON SMART ROADS

Let us analyze the communication involved in our speed limit example. Dictionaries define communication as *exchange of information*. The information exchanged here is the speed limit as shown in Figure 1.

The speed limit information is, within the regulative context, complete and unmistakable. Its spatial, situational and temporal scope, the subjects concerned, the maximum permissible value and the unit of speed (i.e. 30 kilometres per hour)

Fig. 1. Communication of a speed limit.

are explicitly defined. A driver recognizes the speed limit information and, based on their current situational context (surrounding traffic participants, weather conditions, driving skills, etc.), selects a target driving speed.

A well known communication model, proposed in [2], consists of an information source, a transmitter that encodes the message, the channel and a placeholder for noise, a receiver that decodes the message, and a destination. Inspired by this, we model the process of communication in the context of smart roads as depicted in Figure 2.

Logically, communication happens directly on the information level. Physical communication in the real world necessarily takes a detour and requires the following steps:

- *encoding* the information using appropriately placed traffic signs, whose syntax (e.g., appearance, location), and semantic (e.g. meaning, exceptions) are usually defined in applicable regulations known to the communicating partners.
- *transmission* of the signals, in this case via light in direct line of sight.
- *decoding* involving visual perception of the traffic sign (shape, symbols, etc.) and deriving the encoded information.

The communication model in Figure 2 resembles the ISO/OSI layered architecture for network communication [3]: The distinction between logical communication (exchange of information) and physical communication involving (potentially multi-layered) encoding, transmission, and decoding steps can also be found there.

Another resemblance can be found in the DIKW pyramid [4]. The traditional Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom (hence DIKW) pyramid contains these four levels and is often annotated with descriptive verbs that indicate how to progress from one level to the next level above. The DIKW-model has been extended to contain more levels above and below the traditional levels, e.g., [5], [6], to account for additional aspects that were considered important in different fields of application. Several aspects of the DIKW model are duly disputed e.g., [7], but its general idea can sharpen our under-

standing of the abstraction level of the information exchanged in the communication process. An extended DIKW model is shown in Figure 3, which contains the three layers "Data", "Information" and "Knowledge" which appear consistently throughout most adaptations of the traditional DIKW model as well as an additional "Signal" level at the bottom, which is relevant to this discussion. The top level "Action" combines knowledge and context into behaviour.

A smart road service aims at supplementing a participant's perception of the world. Therefore, communication between traffic participants and infrastructure is central. In order to improve aspects of traffic (e.g., safety, flow, density, etc.), two questions must be addressed: First, what content should be communicated? Second, how should the content be represented? This paper addresses the second question.

Looking at the DIKW model, content may potentially be presented at any level of abstraction. However, communication is not practical at all levels. We discuss these levels using our speed limit example, which is traditionally communicated by posting a physical sign at a specific location. Table I maps speed limit aspects to each level.

TABLE I
A 30 KM/H SPEED LIMIT MAPPED TO EACH LEVEL OF A DIKW MODEL.

Level	Description
Signal	numbers 3 and 0 in black on a circular, white and reflective metal plate with a red border
Data	traffic sign "30 km/h speed limit" at specific location
Information	30 km/h max. driving speed, within a defined region, all day, valid for all regular vehicle types
Knowledge	my speed should not exceed 30 km/h
Action	appropriate maneuver plan

One could consider each level of the pyramid representing a different natural language. The same meaning (semantic) might then be communicated in any of these languages. Message content (syntax) would then be the specific wording in that language. There might be advantages or disadvantages

Fig. 2. Model of information exchange between road authority and driver, based on [2].

Fig. 3. DIKW model tailored to smart road services.

in using a particular language.

Presenting content on the *signal* level would involve transmitting all features and characteristics of the traffic sign. Each participant must combine these received features and classify the particular traffic sign. This process is not robust: occlusion, incomplete feature sets, or contradicting features pose problems. Also, equivalent traffic signs may differ in appearance among countries.

Presenting content on the *data* level would involve transmitting the position and type of the traffic sign. This seems natural since it mimics the established style of communication from road authority to the human driver. This reduces robustness problems and is less verbose compared to the *signal* level. But, inferring the speed limit requires additional data, e.g., another (later) traffic sign ending the speed limit such as city limits.

Presenting content on the *information* level would involve transmitting a complete description of the speed limit, including geographic, situational, and temporal scope, addressed vehicle types, and maximum velocity. This leaves little room for interpretation due to inference/classification failures or errors caused by incomplete *data* such as missing the corresponding cancellation sign.

Presenting content on the *knowledge* level would involve transmitting a message like 'your speed should not exceed 30km/h'. This requires that the sender knows something about the receiver. Generally speaking, communication on

the knowledge level requires the sender to have access to additional characteristics like vehicle type, driver's license type, toll sticker, axis load, etc. In our working example, converting information into knowledge is equivalent to the mental step that a human driver takes when recognizing a speed limit sign at a location (information) and concluding that "this particular sign is applicable to me".

Presenting content on the *action* level would involve transmitting recommendations, like 'you should slow down', or even (remote) commands that might reach through to a connected vehicle's braking system. This essentially means that the sender would perform tasks that are traditionally performed by the driver (or an automated driving (AD) function). This is in conflict with international agreements which state that the driver [8] or the AD function [9] has to be in control of their vehicle at all times. Besides legal questions, it is doubtful that proper consideration of the full situational context can be ensured by other entities than the driver.

The discussion above indicates that *presenting content at the information level is most advantageous*. It does not require accessibility of specific characteristics about the receiver of information and therefore steers well clear of all legal issues arising from conflicts regarding driver or AD function responsibility. The responsibility to correctly derive knowledge from information and situational context remains with the driver or an AD function. At the same time it does not merely replicate the established way to communicate, which is difficult to standardize for international applicability and error prone regarding completeness and correctness of the transmitted information.

III. INFORMATION MODELS FOR SMART ROAD SERVICES

The discussion so far focused very much on a singular working example. However, it seems natural to generalize and apply to the broad spectrum of information relevant in (smart) road traffic. As an example, standardization efforts for communication in traffic at the information level in recent years were fruitful and yielded a group of published standards, [10], [11], [12], [13]. These documents define groups of C-ITS messages suitable to express different types of information relevant for smart road services.

Since these standards focus on applications within a declared scope, they, by design, only partially cover the spectrum

of potentially relevant information. In the context of smart roads and autonomous driving, unbelievably diverse situational aspects are relevant for different stakeholders. Stakeholders include traffic participants, vehicle or component manufacturers, insurance, road network operation and maintenance, multimodal traffic planning, and test field operation. Each stakeholder is interested in specific information or aspects of smart road services.

An *information model* for smart road services declares and structures all conceivable relevant information. The notion of an information model is sometimes also referred to in the literature as *data model* or *ontology*.

Given that smart roads and autonomous driving is a highly dynamic and young field of research, the landscape of standards, formats, tools, and methods has not yet converged to a homogeneous, universally accepted, and well-structured state of the art. The platform *connected automated driving*¹ collects about 170 published standards and more than 30 standards in development, among those e.g., Taxonomies for Operational Design Domains (ODD) [14], [15], [16], Scenario representation [17], Safety and Edge Cases [18].

Currently, there is no universally accepted information model covering all conceivable aspects of smart road services. Towards the vision of such a reference information model, we propose a concise set of requirements in section IV that serves as a starting point.

IV. REQUIREMENTS ON INFORMATION MODELS

Different smart road services focus on different sub-sets of information. This might introduce a tendency to application specific sub-sets that express the same information represented in different (and possibly incompatible) ways. A unified reference information model would support the convergence of development efforts and interoperability of systems. Towards such a universally acceptable reference information model, a requirements driven approach appears best suited.

Table II proposes requirements to facilitate the development and standardisation efforts of a reference information model. It intentionally does not address requirements on sensor systems, hardware, transmission technology, vehicles, or business aspects. These requirements strongly depend on the specific implementation of a particular smart road service, conflicting with the goal of this work: exploring general requirements on information models.

The first two requirements in Table II are closely related to the discussion in Section II where an argument for content formulated at the information level is made. The first requirement addresses the distinction between data and information, the second requirement addresses the distinction between information and knowledge. The next three requirements address representation of content. The last requirement introduces another layer of difficulty, because solutions-by-country are not acceptable if smart road services are to be implemented worldwide.

The requirement that content must be *source agnostic* ensures the applicability of any conceivable perception method.

With this requirement met, information can be provided not only by currently available technology but also by future sensors based on novel sensing technologies. This means that perception technology can be changed and updated in the background without requiring changes to the information model or at the receiver side.

Being *receiver agnostic* means that content is formulated such that it imposes no restrictions regarding which receiver can utilize the information. It also means that content is not tailored specifically towards a particular receiver. In our working example, all road users receive the information that there is a speed limit in place at the specified time and spatial region, cf. Table I. However, each road user must determine for themselves whether this speed limit applies to them (i.e., derive specific knowledge from the information).

Self-contained information not only supports consistency but also improves robustness against some errors or misunderstandings. As an example, it is desirable that the temporal and spatial scope of a rule and the rule itself are expressed in one atomic unit of information, as opposed to two or three. In the working example, the speed limit, its value and its spatial and temporal scope are contained within one unit of information. Note that for human drivers, the *beginning* and *end* of a speed limit are traditionally communicated by individual traffic signs. If a human driver misses the end-sign, they often rely on context and deduce the fact from observing the behaviour of other traffic participants. Based on personal judgment and risk-estimation, they may or may not adjust their driving accordingly.

An *unambiguous* information is hard to misunderstand. Traffic laws and regulations are specifically designed to be unambiguous and achieve this goal to a satisfactory degree, e.g., traffic signs can easily be distinguished by humans.

However, existing laws and regulations are not *context-free*. The driver needs additional implicit information to perform driving tasks correctly. For example, most countries use right-hand traffic, some use left-hand traffic. Crossing the border between France and the UK requires the driver to switch to left-hand traffic and also drive through roundabouts clockwise, overtake other vehicles passing on their right etc. Therefore, context-free information should comply to a Chomsky type 2 grammar [19].

Lastly, being *internationally applicable* is a necessary condition for practicality. The requirement is easily stated, but its fulfillment involves significant difficulty. On the one hand, it requires laws and regulations to be self-consistent on both the national and the international level. On the other hand, it calls for an internationally standardized or at least compatible language to express them. A sub-set of this spectrum is already standardized by ETSI, [10], [11], [12], [13], which defines information that meet many, if not all the above mentioned requirements.

Assume these requirements can be met and an agreeable reference information model can be defined as a super-set of relevant information. Then, one can investigate how this reference model relates to the Infrastructure Support Level for Automated Driving (ISAD [20], [21]).

¹<https://www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/standards/standards-collection/>, accessed September 2021

TABLE II
REQUIREMENTS ON INFORMATION AND ITS REPRESENTATION.

Requirement	Description
Source agnostic	Information is presented in a technology neutral way.
Receiver agnostic	Information is valid independent of the receiver.
Self-contained	A piece of information should be complete and atomic.
Unambiguous	Meaning must not be subject to interpretation.
Context-free	Meaning does not depend on the context.
Internationally applicable	The diversity of worldwide road traffic shall be expressible.

V. REFERENCE INFORMATION MODEL, ODD AND ISAD

A reference information model integrates all information that may be relevant for any smart road service. Every service involves solving a number of tasks. Each task requires a specific sub-set of information that has to be made available and aggregated to knowledge (section II) in order to enable decisions to be made and actions to be taken.

Figure 4 shows a Venn diagram of different sets of information as sub-sets of the reference information model (black). In our working example, the application might be cooperative automated cruise control (CACC). A CACC-enabled vehicle automates the task *select driving speed*. Necessary information (blue) for this task include own speed, maximum permissible speed, and the longitudinal dynamics of the preceding vehicles. This information might be acquired by on-board sensors (orange, e.g., radar, camera) or by digital services provided by others (green, e.g., infrastructure, vehicles). The task can be performed only if the entire sub-set of necessary information is made available to the CACC-enabled vehicle.

Fig. 4. Information in a smart road service example: The required information (blue) is covered by the superset of on-board sensors (orange) and digital services (green). Note that these sets may vary over time.

Infrastructure Support Level for Automated Driving (ISAD) describes the information sub-set provided by the infrastructure, together with a *Quality of Service*. Thus, ISAD level helps the CACC-enabled vehicle determine if the necessary

information will be available (by combination of on-board sensors and digital services) in the road section ahead. The ISAD level therefore literally supports automated driving by supplementing additional information or, at least, assuring to stay within the ODD.

When making information available to the drivers and automated vehicles, the Quality of Service (QoS) aspect is worth further consideration. The term QoS encompasses attributes of the information such as accuracy, reliability, age of the information, etc. QoS requirements differ among different information groups. To name an example: The requirements on the acceptable age of the information strongly vary among different information groups. For non dynamic information (e.g. long term construction sites) surely a considerably higher message age can be accepted, than for dynamic information (e.g. collective perception information or traffic light status). Thus, above all, the (guaranteed) availability of information or information groups at a certain QoS is a critical aspect for automated driving.

Recently a scheme for infrastructure support for automated driving (ISAD) was presented in the scope of the INFRAMIX² project and was well received on a European level. The implications and exact definitions of such a scheme are, however, still disputed [22], [23], [24]. Following the logic and reasoning presented in this work, it is obvious that the ISAD discussion is a discussion about information availability. More precisely it is about the above mentioned QoS aspect of information.

For a future automated driving system it will be essential to decide if its ODD in a foreseeable future scenario will be fulfilled. That decision hinges on knowing which information and QoS it can expect to be accessible on the road sections ahead. Making a new sub-set of information available can improve infrastructure support and thereby increase the ISAD level. For instance the current ISAD scheme presented in [20], [21] distinguishes between *static information* of ISAD D and *dynamic information* of ISAD C, which in our approach refers to different information sub-sets as discussed above. Moreover even the availability of up-to date information on the current state of QoS (the current ISAD level) might be crucial information itself. To name an example: If a sensor or system providing the infrastructure information is malfunctioning, the

²<https://www.inframix.eu>

notification about a reduced QoS (a lower ISAD level) might be crucial for an automated vehicle relying on the - now unavailable - information. Thus, the ISAD level itself is a dynamic information.

Note, that the current ISAD concept as proposed in [22], [23] does not focus on information in the most strict sense and also includes content on the data level. Further, the scheme is not formulated entirely source agnostic and therefore conflicting with at least two of the requirements stated above, indicating the need for re-formulation.

VI. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

This work formulates requirements on information models for smart road services. Based on a layered communication model, it is argued that communication between participants at the information level (as opposed to data or signal levels of the DIKW pyramid) is most advantageous.

The field of smart roads and automated driving is a very young field of research, with much ongoing work on standards and classification schemes. An important one is the recently presented Infrastructure Support for Automated Driving (ISAD) concept. Although the formulation of this concept filled an open gap and partly covers the Quality of Service (QoS) idea, the currently proposed formulation of the ISAD levels is not entirely satisfying when compared with the findings of this work.

It was made clear that the discussion about smart road services necessarily should focus on information availability, accessibility and QoS, rather than on the existence of specific infrastructure elements. We therefore propose to center the ISAD concept solely around the communicated information and QoS, but agnostic to the solution providing the necessary information. Thus, we argue that a well defined reference information model is the foundation of the ISAD concept, rather than physical/digital infrastructure element lists.

An information-centered ISAD service would allow automated vehicles to evaluate if all the necessary information will be available on a specific road section. Thus, the vehicle would be able to determine a priori if it is capable of driving the road section ahead avoiding foreseeable ODD violations. Additionally, the receiver agnostic representation of information greatly reduces system complexity of an ISAD service on the provider side. Of course, designing and providing an ISAD service requires knowledge about the information needed by automated driving systems. But, contrary to previous ISAD concepts, it is not necessary that the ISAD service provider understands the specifics of vehicle system ODDs.

Considering the requirements identified in this work, the specification of a reference information model will be challenging. In future work, the authors will continue laying the basis for such a reference information model.

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